

RENEWABLE ENERGY and IT'S TRANSITION

Since the inception of man on earth, man has put to use various sources of energy (whether renewable or non-renewable). Renewable energy is any form of energy that can be regenerated after use, while non-renewable energy forms are forms of energy that cannot be wholly regenerated after use. These energy (renewable or non-renewable) have different sources. However, renewable energy sources supply 14% of the total world energy demand(UNDP) as cited in Panwar N. L., Kaushik S. C., & Kothari S. (2019).

Renewable sources of energy are considered as clean sources of energy, and optimal use of these sources of energy (renewable energy) minimize environmental impacts, produce minimum secondary wastes and are sustainable based on current and future economic and social societal needs. There are three major sources of renewable energy, namely: fossil fuels, renewable resources and nuclear resources(Demirbas A) as cited in Panwar et. Al. (2019).

We see that renewable energy sources can be used for production of energy, over and again without depletion of the energy sources. Renewable energy sources include but not limited to : solar energy, wind energy, biomass, hydropower, geothermal and marine energy. Amongst all aforementioned, solar energy remains the most reliable source of energy to man.

Clean, domestic and renewable energy is commonly accepted as the key for future life, not only for Turkey, but also for the World(Kentel E. & Ediger V. S., 1997). Underlying any binding and universal agreement on greenhouse gas emissions to limit the average global temperature increase since pre-industrial times to 2°C, is the belief that there is sufficient carbon-free energy to meet our future needs(IPPC 2015:Jacobsin and Delucchi, 2011) as cited in Honnery. D & Moriarty P. (2016).

There has been a change from the use of fossil fuels to renewable energy sources and this is called "Energy Transition." Given the severity of the threat posed by the anthropogenic climate change, which is in large part driven by fossil fuel combustion, it is becoming widely recognized that societies need a transition in how they produce and consume energy(Bell E. S & York. R, 2019). We find practical application of fossil fuel combustion in our day-to-day activities from automobiles to engines in industries which contribute greatly to environmental pollution and even ozone layer depletion.

A very good example of energy transition is the generation of electrical energy from solar energy using solar panels. Unlike the early ages when electricity was only generated from hydropower. We can say that transition away from fossil fuels to renewable energy , may be in its early stage , and also, the use of biomass as a material expanded even more dramatically as a result of fossil fuel-powered machinery(Bell E.S. & York. R., 2019).

An important reason for replacing fossil fuels with renewable energy is to promote ecological sustainability —in particular, to minimize further climate change. The natural World provides many ecosystem services, such as provision of food, freshwater and climate regulation, but land-intensive energy systems, particularly hydro electricity and bioenergy, inevitably reduce such service provision(Honnery D. & Moriarty P., 2016). Due to the above stated reason, implementation of renewable energy usage will save us(humans) and our ecosystem from suffering severe damages.

The foregoing deals with renewable energy and its transition over the years. It unveils the advantages of implementing the use of renewable energy over non-renewable energy. From this work, we come to know that in few years time, with proper implementation of the use of renewable energy, there will be reduction in environmental pollution, thus making our ecosystem a safer place to live in. Therefore, I suggest that the both Government and non-governmental organisations see to it that renewable energy dominates the use of non-renewable energy in our society by raising platforms that promote use of renewable energy.

References :

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